

blight and stem borer.

It has green foliage without basal leaf sheath pigmentation and can be used as a marker for identifying shattered grains of Janki, which has a purple basal leaf sheath, in deepwater plots.

In 1982-86 deepwater rice yield trials, average yield at Pusa experiment station was 1.6 t/ha, compared to 1.4 t/ha for check variety Janki (Table 2). In 77 deepwater minikit tests in farmers' fields 1984-85, it yielded an average 2.1 t/ha compared to 1.8 t/ha of check. In all India coordinated trials during 1984, its average yield at deepwater locations was 2.4 t/ha, compared to 2.1 t/ha of checks. Maximum yields were 3.2 t/ha in 1985 on-farm trial at Deoria Kothi, East Champaran, and 3.7 t/ha in 1984 at Malda, West Bengal. Breeder seed is being produced at Pusa, Bihar. □

Table 1. Varietal reaction to diseases and pests in Bihar, India.

Variety	Disease score ^a				
	Tungro	Brown spot	Bacterial blight	Sheath rot	Stem borer
Sudha	3	3	5	1	5
Janki	3	5	7	3	6
Br 8	7	5	7	7	6
T141	7	5	7	7	6

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale.

Table 2. Yield performance of Sudha in Pusa, India, 1982-86.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)						
	1982	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	Average
Sudha	2.0	2.1	2.0	1.0	0.8	1.7	1.6
Janki	1.8	1.7	1.9	0.8	0.8	1.6	1.4
CD (0.05)	0.25	0.26	0.49	0.33	ns	—	
CV (%)	19.4	8.3	17.5	19.0	47.9	—	
Maximum water depth (cm)	50	30	80	120	90	95	

NC493, a promising variety for rainfed deepwater areas

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The 1985 Annual Rice Workshop of the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, has recommended NC493 (IET8989); a pureline selection identified at Chinsurah, as a promising variety for semideep water (50-100 cm) in West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, and Tripura. In 9 state adaptive trials 1979-82, NC493 averaged 39% higher grain yield than checks Pankaj, Mahsuri, and Tilakkachari (see table).

NC493 is photoperiod sensitive and flowers in late Oct. It is medium tall (150 cm) and tillers moderately (7-9). The panicle is about 25 cm long with good exertion and golden color glumes. The glumes are 10.1 mm long; shape index is 3.9; 1,000 grain weight, 23 g. Seed dormancy is strong. It is resistant to bacterial blight and blast, moderately resistant to brown spot, and moderately susceptible to sheath blight, bacterial leaf streak, and yellow stem borer.

NC493 yielded an average 3.1 t/ha (2.4 t/ha for check) over 46 locations and has been recommended for minikit demonstration trials in farmers' fields. □

Performance of NC493 in state and national trials, India, 1979-85.

Trial	Sites	Local check	Yield (t/ha)		Max water depth (cm)
			NC493	Local check	
State adaptive	Nine sites	<i>1979-82</i>			
		Pankaj, Mahsuri, and Tilakkachari	3.9	2.8	75
PVT-5	Chinsurah Cuttack Patna Pusa Gaghraghat	<i>1983</i>			
		IET7976	4.6	2.5	46
		Tilakkachari	4.2	2.6	42
		Tilakkachari	2.6	1.8	na
		Tilakkachari	1.6	1.5	65
		Tilakkachari	0.7	0	60
UVT-5	Malda Hyderabad Cuttack Sabour Karimganj Bhubaneswar Pulla	<i>1984</i>			
		CN540 (Suresh)	5.0	4.2	40
		IET9168	3.9	2.4	50
		CR210-1018	3.5	0.7	na
		Jantu	3.1	2.2	na
		NC492 (Sabita)	2.6	2.2	na
		OR142-105	2.3	1.9	100
Physiology screening	Four sites	Mahsuri	1.5	1.2	70
		NC492 (Sabita)	3.1	2.7	na
UVT-5	Arundhutinagan Patna Malda Cuttack Gaghraghat Aduthurai Masodha Ranital Karimganj Pulla	<i>1985</i>			
		Pizam	7.4	4.5	na
		Janki (C64-117)	3.6	1.8	na
		Janki (C64-117)	3.6	2.7	70
		CR1030	3.0	3.1	na
		Madhukar	2.8	2.0	53
		CR1009	2.6	2.6	50
		TI00	2.4	0.8	34
		CR 1009	2.3	1.2	45
		Janki (C64-117)	2.0	1.3	90
		PLA1100	1.0	0.7	70
Physiology screening	Five sites	NC492 (Sabita)	3.1	2.8	na
	Mean		3.1	2.1	

^ana = not available.